

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B357
Date: 16 April 2008
Take Off: 09:47:24Z
Landing: 15:11:25Z
Flight Time 5h24m01s

Campaign: ADIENT

Operating Area: East coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Megan Northway	University of Reading
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	SWS / SHIMS	Stuart Rodgers	Met Office
8	CVI	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office
9	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
10	SP2	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester
11	Wet Neph	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
12			

Flight Track:

B357 Track 16-APR-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B357
 Date: 16/4/08
 Project: ADIENT
 Location: UK West Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093954		power change	0.12 kft	123	
094131		Taxi	0.11 kft	123	
094415		asp open	0.12 kft	175	
094724		T/O	0.10 kft	032	from Cranfield
102522	103216	Profile 1	16.0 - 10.0 kft	227	Interrupted
103341	104743	Profile 1	10.1 - 2.6 kft	320	Resumed
104220		Profile 1	2.7 kft	323	500 ft/min
104544		bbr	0.84 kft	356	exposed
104834	111002	Run 1.1	0.33 - 0.36 kft	012	
111029	111316	Profile 2	0.63 - 2.8 kft	359	at end r1.1
111316	112036	Profile 3	2.8 - -.12 kft	297	
112121	113835	Run 1.2	0.31 - 0.33 kft	350	
113835	113923	Profile 4	0.33 - 0.04 kft	016	
113923	114503	Run 2.1	0.04 - 0.05 kft	014	
114526	115401	Run 3.1	0.31 - 0.30 kft	016	
115544	121854	Run 3.2	0.31 - 0.37 kft	145	
122201	123944	Run 3.3	0.36 - 0.32 kft	028	
122617		qnh 1020	0.36 kft	016	
124952	130948	Run 3.4	0.32 kft	181	
131106	133129	Run 3.5	0.36 - 0.37 kft	047	
131448		Run 3.5	0.36 kft	022	on 40 nmi track
133314	133425	Profile 5	0.29 - -.15 kft	217	
133426	134323	Profile 6	-.15 - 5.0 kft	207	
134456	135435	Run 4.1	5.0 kft	302	
135604	135941	Profile 7	2.0 - -.08 kft	103	
140036	142331	Run 5.1	0.31 - 0.34 kft	127	
142430	142636	Run 5.2	0.33 - 0.32 kft	278	
142637	143343	Profile 8	0.32 - 4.8 kft	277	
151125		Land	0.23 kft	035	at Cranfield

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B357 Track 16-APR-08

EGTC -> EGTE - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-4 Expires: Thursday, 08 May 2008.

Scale: 1:2015681 (1 inch = 27.64 naut mi). Printed on 15 Apr 2008

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.3.0.0

**ADIENT Flight B357
FAAM sortie brief**

Wednesday 16 April, 2008

Operating Area: A and B

Sortie Objectives: To identify and characterize aerosol plumes and optical properties with a combination of in situ and radiation measurements. Mission critical instruments: PCASP, Wet nephelometer, ToF-AMS

Weather: High pressure situated over Shetland Is. and low position SW of Iceland is forecast to bring SE flow across the UK. Fronts to the west of Ireland are forecast to remain stationary through the day though there is some chance of cirrus in advance of the fronts affecting the operating region. Convection over land areas is forecast but little cloud is predicted to be present over the Irish Sea area. Easterly winds should advect aerosol some aerosol plumes off the E. coast of the UK. High aerosol loadings and clear skies needed for radiation work. Plumes from the Bristol and Cardiff areas are expected in the Severn estuary and off the coast of south Wales; the Birmingham plume is forecast off the north Wales coast; and the Manchester-Liverpool plume is expected in the Dee estuary and Morecambe Bay areas. This plume is anticipated to be positioned to extend as far north as the Isle of Man.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Cranfield at 10z (11 am local)
3. Transit at FL150 towards waypoint 48 (north Devon). [30 mins at transit]
4. Upon reaching point 48 perform descent profile at 1000 ft/ min above 3000 ft and 500 ft/min below 3000 ft to arrive at waypoint 47 at minimum altitude [20 min, T=50]
5. Ascend to 500ft and perform an SLR clockwise around the SW coast of England and Wales (avoiding any low cloud where possible). Suggested routing:
Waypoints 47-> 37-> 49-> 50->51-> 52->53-> 54->55
[75 min, T=125]
6. Where aerosol conditions are appropriate (currently predicted to be in a box bounded by 53-54-EGNH-EGGP), conduct either
 - a) in situ plume characterisation work, or
 - b) radiation characterisation work, assuming no cloud.
[up to 120 min, T245]

a). In situ sampling: conduct a raster pattern inside the operating area as dictated by the aerosol plumes (see suggestion above), this will comprise a series

of SLRs cross plume and at multiple heights in the boundary layer and immediately above.

Repetitions of these runs should be conducted at different distances downwind of the plume source, connected by SLRs in the BL plume along the plume centreline.

Once the plume centreline has been established an SLR along the plume centre may be carried out in the BL.

b). Radiation perform series of SLRs for radiation work outlined below between points A and B (roughly 100 km apart). Suggested flight pattern:

- a. Profile ascent from low level at A (i.e. minimum safe altitude) towards B until nephelometer suggests you are well above aerosol layers (anticipated FL80) at 500ft per minute below 3000ft and 1000ft/min above 3000ft (travelling 80km in this time). Continue to point B at high level if necessary, with SWS and SHIMS pointing upwards. [~10 mins, t=10].
 - b. At point B perform FAAM outside turn to re-orient on a reciprocal heading [5 mins, t=15]
 - c. SLR of 15 minutes at FL70 (or above aerosol) back towards A. SWS and SHIMS to point downwards during this time. [15 mins, t=30]
 - d. Perform a series of 1-2 orbits at maximum bank angle at point A [10 mins, t=40]
 - e. Broken profile descent in region of point A until within aerosol layer [10 mins, t=50]
 - f. Turn onto heading towards B [5 mins, t=55]
 - g. Perform a SLR from A to B within the aerosol layer for in-situ sampling.[15 mins, t=70]
 - h. FAAM turn and broken profile descent over point B to low level (100ft). [5 mins, t=75]
 - i. 15 min SLR at low level (100ft) towards point A with SWS and SHIMS pointing upwards for first 10 minutes and downwards for final 5 minutes (to get sea state and albedo) [15 mins, t=90]
 - j. Ascend to minimum safe altitude (500 ft at 50 degrees) and perform 1-2 orbits at point A [10 min, t=100]
7. Perform descent profile at 1000 ft/ min above 3000 ft and 500 ft/min below 3000 ft from minimum altitude
[20 min, T=295]
8. Transit and land Cranfield [T=320].
9. Perform pirouette as in step #1

Addition operational instructions:

Please remember to close off PSAP valve when going through cloud!
SWS/SHIMS operator – please see special instructions in step #6

Tuesday 15 April 2008 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Wednesday 16 April 2008 12UTC
Surface: Mean sea level pressure / 12hr Accumulated precipitation (VT-6h/VT+6h)

Tuesday 15 April 2008 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Wednesday 16 April 2008 12UTC
Low, L+M, Medium, M+H, High, H+L, H+M+L clouds

Aerosol

At 14Z on 16/ 4/2008, from 03Z on 15/ 4/2008

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page ⁴.....

Flight No **B.357** Date **16 Apr 2008** Name **Megan Northway** Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:40					718 cu - Cranfield (early T10)
9:48					T10 Cranfield
9:49					Cloud top 2800ft
9:53					FL100
					initial profile - nephelometer
10:03					
10:10		FL160			Approaching Bristol Channel from E
10:12		FL160			SP2 pump flow close to zero
10:13		"	261		(contrails persisting above) to north
10:19		"	227		heading SW into Bristol Channel
10:21		"	227		over sea, turbulence
10:26	PI	FL160 FL160			Sturdy profile towards point 50
10:27	PI		226		some mid-level / low level cloud ahead
10:29	PI				Jeff taking photos...
10:33	PI	FL100			Profile interrupt - turning to NW to point 50
10:33:41	PI	FL100 - Soft			PI recommenced wind 69°
10:36	PI	~8100ft	322		Layer of haze ahead at low level
10:40	PI	4600ft			Layer of pollution just above Zoom (~6000ft)

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page ... 10,973!

Flight No **B** 357 Date 16 Apr 2008 Name Megan Northway Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					2500 ft top of BL
10:45	P1	500ft			passing over ^{small} cloud neph ~ 40m ⁻¹
10:46	P1	700ft			CO = 200 ppb
10:47	P1				some cloud overhead 1/8 Cu
10:48:34	P1	500ft			Beautiful day! CO flat at 200 ppb
10:52	R1	500ft			4.5 ppb SO ₄ from AMS
10:54	"	"			passing St Davids to right 2/8 Cu above
10:57	R1	"			passing over cruise liner to left No of Strumbol point
10:59	R1	"			out of plume chemistry lower CO = 170 ppb, neph = 20 m ⁻¹ NO ₃ < 0.5 ug from AMS
11:11:2	P2	500 - 3000ft			saw both to 3000 ft
	P2	1700ft			some Cu around ~ 2/8 coverage
11:13	P2	3000ft			aerosol well mixed ^{point}
11:15	P3	3000ft - 500ft			here; low values on neph, SO ₄ ^{point} back down =
11:20	P3	~1000ft			passed banti island at end of Ilyn peninsula
11:21		50ft			end of P3 at 50ft

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B**..... Date April 16 2008 Name Megan Noetmy Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:21:21	R1	500ft			clear skies above
11:27:00	R1.2	"			SWS lost 1R part of detector - Vis part OK
11:33:00	"	500		53.5°N, -4.8°E	plume picking up now - AMS, SP2, chemistry 4.5 µg NO3 - on point w/ aerosol model ~100 m ⁻¹
11:37	"	"			AMS seeing >10 µg/m ³ total aerosol
11:37	"	"			passing point 53 - coast of N Ire l.
11:38:35	P4	280ft			avoiding ^(low) cloud - dipping to 200ft AMS saw ~20 µg/m ³
11:42	R	"			SP2 sees not much BC - lots of scattering particles E. of Belfast
11:45		280ft			staying at 280 below cloud
11:46	R3.1	500ft			back up to 500ft
11:51	R3.1	"			passing waypoint 60 - a lot of cirrus / high cloud / contrails above.
11:55		500ft			End of 3.1 - turning towards UK coast for parallel track
11:57	3.2				↗ short bit E-W Galway to left of aircraft
12:12	3.3				↖ back on parallel track plume picked up

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No B.357

Date 16 Apr

Name M. Naethuray

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:19	3.2				end of Run - turning for another parallel run
12:20	3.2	500ft	70		polluter visible on horizon
12:24		500ft	27		
12:30	3.3	"	16		AMS, nephelometer going up (blue) neph ~ 115 m
					Passing Isle of man
12:33	3.3	"	19		SP2 seeing lots of BC
12:38	3.3	"			back out of plume
12:40	end of 3.3 * (no profile)				up to 5000 ft to go around Isle of man - CO cal
12:49		500ft - 500ft			SP2 was off for a moment - back on
12: 50 ^{49:52}	R3.4	500ft			start of Run
R53	"	500ft	205		rounding Isle of Man
13:01	"	"			passed ship (enormous)
13:02	"	"			back in plume CO = 300ppb m59 organics - high
					~ 53°N plume?
13:12	3.5	500ft			passing Hollyhead Island
13:22	3.5	"			Rigs in the area
13:25					out of plume
					O ₃ anticorrelated w/ SO ₄ in AMS
13:27	3.5	"			better visibility here

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No B.357 Date Apr 16, 2008 Name M. Northway Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:31	35				end of run - turning back onto reciprocal run
13:34	P5	500-50			profiling ^{down} on reciprocal track
13:35	P6	50-5000ft			" up " " " "
13:39	P6	2500ft	186		relatively clear skies, although a little bit of hazy cirrus / contrails around
13:44	P6				end of P6 - turning right away from UK on perpendicular track to previous parallel runs
13:44:46	R4.1	5000ft			perpendicular track
13:57	P7	2000ft - 1000ft			Orbit Descent, + profile from 2000ft to 1000ft
14:00	P7	~1000ft			birds in the way - abrupt climb
	R5.1	500ft			parallel track to last at 500ft
14:05	R5.1	500ft			skies are relatively clear - a little "cirrus haze"
					plume picking up again
14:11		500ft			visibility much lower - downwind of Manchester
14:13	R5.1	"			maximum BC - down wind of rigs
14:23:31	R5.1	"			end of Run - turning on reciprocal
	R5.2				turning back on reciprocal before profile climb
14:27	P8	500-5000ft			profile climbs for transit - over rigs

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 357

Date: 16 apr 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	09:55 log started after t/o due early t/o FFSSP running, recording on, signal and annulus values appear stable SID1 running, logging to B357-1.srd Pcasp running, heater on, motor on, ref 8.4 2dc running 2dp running																
094724																T/O	
101100																Rearm 2 1 command to reduce 2dp logging due noise. Oat -20C	
101600	9	0.09	84	1		0	0	noise								Fl160 towards end of transit	
102522	9	0.09	85	1		0	0	noise								Start P1 fl 160	
	63	0.1	85	1		0	0	noise								Fl140	
	29	0.1	85	1		0	0	noise								Fl120	
103216	77	0.1	85	1		0	0	noise								Fl100	
																Profile interrupted	
	46	0.1	85	1		0	0	noise								Fl100	
	385	0.1	85	3		0	0	0	0							Fl80	
103800																Rearm 2 8 - 2dp now ok	
	95	0.1	85	1		0	0	0	0							Fl60	
	915	0.1	85	3		0	0	0	0							Fl30	
	747	0.1	85	20		0	0	0	0							Fl10	
104743	1200	0.1	86	30		0	0	0	0							End p1	
104834	822	0.1	86	20		0	0	0	0							Start r1.1 500ft	
105200	1700	0.1	88	10		0	0	0	0								
105400	1200	0.1	88	10		0	0	0	0								
110000	406	0.1	88	5		0	0	0	0								
110500	580	0.1	89	5		0	0	0	0								
111000	811	0.1	89	5		0	0	0	0							End run 1.1 start p2 500	
111314	410	0.1	89	10		0	0	0	0							3000 end p2, start p3	
112036	400	0.1	90	10		0	0	0	0							End p3 50ft	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 357

Date: 16 apr 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
112121	360	0.1	90	10		0	0	0	0							Start run 1.2 500ft	
113300	930	0.1	91	10		0	0	0	0								
113500	1800	0.1	92	10		0	0	0	0								
113835	1380	0.1	92	10		0	0	0	0							End run 1.2	
113923	2765	0.1	93	10		0	0	0	0							Star run 2.1	
114500	1160	0.1	93	10		0	0	0	0							End run 2.1	
114526	1081	0.1	94	10		0	0	0	0							Start run 3.1	
115000	550	0.1	94	10		0	0	0	0								
115401	520	0.1	94	5		0	0	0	0							End run 3.1	
115544	578	0.1	94	5		0	0	0	0							Start run 3.2	
120500	790	0.1	95	5		0	0	0	0								
121000	2337	0.1	96	10		0	0	0	0								
121500	1129	0.1	97	10		0	0	0	0								
121854	1256	0.1	98	10		0	0	0	0							End run 3.2	
122201	1005	0.1	98	10		0	0	0	0							Start run 3.3	
122500	1000	0.1	99	5		0	0	0	0								
123000	1925	0.1	99	10		0	0	0	0								
123500	650	0.1	100	5		0	0	0	0								
123944	600	0.1	100	5		0	0	0	0							End run 3.3	
124952	696	0.1	100	3		0	0	0	0							Start run 3.4	
125500	800	0.1	101	5		0	0	0	0								
130000	1800	0.1	102	10		0	0	0	0								
130500	950	0.1	102	5		0	0	0	0								
130948	1072	0.1	102	5		0	0	0	0							End run 3.4	
131106	1112	0.1	102	5		0	0	0	0							Start run 3.5	
131500	650	0.1	102	5		0	0	0	0								
132000	1900	0.1	103	10		0	0	0	0								
132500	1139	0.1	103	5		0	0	0	0								
133000	687	0.1	103	3		0	0	0	0								
133129	656	0.1	103	3		0	0	0	0							End run 3.5	
133314																Start profile 5	
133425	728	0.1	104	3		0	0	0	0							50ft end profile 5 . start profile 6	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

B357_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

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07:50:27.90 --- - - - -
07:50:27.90 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:50:27.90 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:50:27.90 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B357
07:50:27.90 --- - - - -
07:50:41.75 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:50:49.26 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:50:55.47 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:51:00.81 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:51:05.54 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:51:05.55 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:51:15.57 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:51:21.60 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:51:24.94 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:51:28.05 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:51:28.05 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:51:35.80 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:51:43.33 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:51:47.51 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:51:47.52 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:51:53.24 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:52:07.61 LSH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
07:52:07.62 LSH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
07:52:14.75 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
07:52:14.76 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
07:52:32.15 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:52:39.13 SWS - 250 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
08:11:32.63 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
08:11:32.64 LSH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
08:11:40.90 LSH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
08:11:40.91 LSH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
08:13:11.17 --- - - - - *** LSH NIR baseline is very high: 10000
counts
08:13:50.16 SWS - - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
08:13:56.72 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:14:09.78 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:14:22.87 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:14:24.54 SWS 173.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:14:30.91 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:14:32.57 SWS -1.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:14:52.83 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
08:29:31.56 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:29:37.38 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:29:49.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:30:01.71 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:30:05.51 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:30:43.70 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:31:06.46 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:07.91 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:31:18.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:19.72 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:31:25.38 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:31:25.39 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:31:30.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:30.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:31:41.89 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:44.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:44:01.96 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:44:03.40 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:46:36.46 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 106.528
08:46:37.58 SWS 106.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:51:06.19 SWS 106.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:51:07.32 SWS -4.3 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:51:13.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:51:14.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:51:17.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

08:51:18.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:51:21.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:24.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:53:43.60	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:56:09.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** OPERATOR: STUART ROGERS
09:37:36.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:37.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:37:42.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:43.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:37:46.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:48.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:37:56.18	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:37:59.91	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:40:11.02	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
09:40:11.02	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
09:40:16.30	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
09:40:16.31	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
09:40:24.26	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
09:40:24.26	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
09:40:30.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:30.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:30.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:31.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:40:31.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:40:33.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:40:36.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:39.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:41:38.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** Taxiing
09:44:45.49	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:49:04.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** T/O 0947-ish
09:55:26.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:26.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:26.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:27.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:27.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:27.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:28.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:29.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:30.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:49.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:49.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:49.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:56.76	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
09:55:56.76	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
09:56:04.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:04.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:53.36	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
10:05:56.56	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:06:01.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:02.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:13.17	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 30ms.
10:06:16.91	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
10:06:19.67	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
10:06:22.10	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
10:06:26.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:27.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:27.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:42.78	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:07:46.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:47.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:01.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:01.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:01.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:02.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:02.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:02.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:04.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:04.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:15:05.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:08.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:08.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:08.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:32.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** Profile descent
10:33:54.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:54.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:54.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:56.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:56.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:57.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:31.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:47:45.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:45.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:46.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:47.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:47.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:48.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:13.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** Endof profile
10:48:50.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
10:51:30.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:54:23.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:54:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:55:06.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:55:22.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:55:42.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:56:27.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:56:41.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:56:44.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:57:15.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:58:09.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:58:16.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:58:31.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:59:01.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:01.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:01.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:02.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:02.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:04.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:07.68	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:59:10.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:12.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:11.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
11:10:20.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** P
11:10:26.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:26.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:26.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:27.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:27.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:28.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:42.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:13:02.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** Patchy cloud overhead
11:13:29.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** P down
11:20:39.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:39.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:39.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:20:40.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:20:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:20:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:28.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
11:23:38.79	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
11:23:43.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:45.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:54.07	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
11:25:15.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** Suspected loss of SWS NIR
11:28:30.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:36.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
11:28:47.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:28:58.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:29:25.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:25.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:25.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:26.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:29:26.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:29:26.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:29:27.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:27.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:28.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:35.68	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:29:41.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:43.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:47.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:48.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:51.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:53.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:28.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS restarted - NIR is back
11:38:41.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
11:38:55.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** P4
11:38:59.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:39:29.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
11:39:35.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:40:09.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:40:56.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** Patchy cloud above
11:41:30.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:44:49.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:45:08.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:45:09.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
11:45:36.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 500ft
11:46:07.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:08.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:08.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:08.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:09.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:10.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:18.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:20.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:10.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
11:54:14.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:14.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:14.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:16.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:16.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:17.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:52.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:54:59.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:55:50.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
12:10:04.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:04.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:05.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:06.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:06.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:17.60	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:10:20.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:22.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:35.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:15:38.15	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:15:39.90	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:15:42.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:50.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:53.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:53.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:54.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:55.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:55.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:56.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:58.88	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:18:00.62	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

12:18:02.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:16.34	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
12:18:19.73	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:18:23.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:25.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:02.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
12:19:07.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:07.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:07.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:09.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:09.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:09.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:08.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 500ft
12:36:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:50.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:50.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:50.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:51.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:52.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:52.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:58.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:00.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:01.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:51.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
12:42:55.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:55.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:55.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:57.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:57.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:57.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:59.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:59.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:00.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:00.30	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:43:02.08	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:43:05.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:05.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:05.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:43.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:43.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:43.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:45.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:45.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:46.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:47.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:47.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:48.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:48.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:47:50.66	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:47:55.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:55.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:55.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:18.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:49:56.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
13:05:57.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:05:57.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:05:57.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:05:57.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:05:59.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:05:59.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:05:59.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:04.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:10.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:09:25.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:09:55.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:09:58.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
13:10:07.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:10:33.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:10:42.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

13:10:50.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:10:59.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:11:22.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:11:23.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
13:26:55.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:55.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:55.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:56.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:56.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:58.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:36.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
13:31:54.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:43:25.79	---	-	-	-	-	***
13:43:25.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:25.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:25.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:27.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:27.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:28.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:34.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:37.77	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:43:39.55	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:41.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:06.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 5000ft
13:54:41.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
13:56:09.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:09.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:09.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:13.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:56:15.22	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:56:15.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:15.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:15.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:17.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:17.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:18.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:18.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:18.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:18.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:20.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:20.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:21.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:21.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:22.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:22.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:22.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:38.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run
14:15:46.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:46.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:46.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:47.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:47.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:49.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:34.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:22:53.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:23:35.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
14:23:38.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:39.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:40.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:40.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:41.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:01.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:24:40.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:24:44.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 500ft
14:25:03.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:25:11.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:26:41.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
14:47:28.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:47:28.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:28.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:29.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:30.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:31.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:31.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:31.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:31.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:33.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:33.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:34.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:20.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:04:46.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:04:59.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:05:30.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:05:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:05:49.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:06:03.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:06:54.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:01.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:07.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:20.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:35.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:43.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:49.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:53.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:07:57.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:08:07.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:08:20.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:08:47.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:09:13.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:09:19.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:09:33.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:09:59.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:20.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:29.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:46.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:57.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:11:29.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:11:59.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:12:20.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:20.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:21.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:32.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:12:34.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:12:37.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:12:49.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 102.109
15:12:50.26	SWS	102.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:12:58.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
15:13:02.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
15:13:02.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B** 357

Date 16/4/2008

Operator's name: D. TIDDEMAN

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:29	P1	12.5kft	13.0	0.0	26.0	26.0	18°	Switch chiller on - And control...
10:36	P1	7.5kft	12.6	0.0	16.5	23.5	10°	
10:49	Run1	500ft	11.3	34.1	65.9	25°	35°	
10:54	Run1	500ft	12.4	30.8	45.9	24°	17°	Aerosols dropped off during run
11:01	Run1	500ft	12.3	24.6	77.7	25°	38°	
11:10	"	"	11.3	26.2	40.3	24°	15°	
11:11	Run1-2	500ft	12.4	25.6	80.6	24.5°	40°	T, see if I can control it at higher humidity than 80%
11:25	"	"	12.3	24.6	90.1	25°	44.3°	
11:35	"	"	12.2	29.5	50.0	24.5°	14.8°	
11:42	Run1-2	250ft	12.3	32.4	90.1	25°	44.7°	
11:44	R3-1	250ft	12.2	27.9	53.1	24.5°	18°	
11:55	R3-1	"	12.3	27.5	88.7	25°	43.6	
12:02	R3-2	"	12.3	26.9	50.7	24.5°	19	
12:08	R3-2	"	12.2	29.8	89.3	25°	43.7	
12:15	R3-2	"	12.2	30.5	54.0	24.5°	18.5	
12:23	R3-3	"	12.2	30.5	91.2	25°	44.1	
12:34	"	"	12.2	26.9	50	24.5°	14.6	
12:39	R3-3	"	12.2	25.9	89.7	25°	43.7	
12:52	R3-4	"	12.1	25.3	39.1	24.5°	11.2	
12:59	"	"	12.1	26.2	87.4	25°	43°	

Flight:

B357

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B357

Date: 16 April 2008

Instruments

1. GIN noticed to be reporting erroneous data following take-off (had us over the Isle of Man and heading North East!). System reset and worked fine afterwards.

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B357:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Sortie brief	Sortie brief not currently available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI log	Log not currently available
SP2 log	SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Oct 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102145_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112145_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122145_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132145_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_142145_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102136_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112136_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122136_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132136_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_142136_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102132_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112132_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122132_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132132_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_142132_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102141_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112141_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122141_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132141_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_142141_1hz.avi

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132145_1hz was corrupt

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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